

SYSTEMS OF REPRESENTATION: A PEDAGOGICAL MODEL FOR THE EDUCATION OF DESIGN IN THE INFORMATION AGE.

Abstract

The course SDR: SISTEMAS DE REPRESENTACIÓN (Systems of Representation)¹, is the last stage of a line of work which has the objective of integrating information technologies in the education of architecture in a meaningful way. A distinctive mark of this pedagogic approach has been to look upon computer technology as an opportunity to rethink the methods, contents and goals of architectural education, in the light of contemporary culture.

The course is structured in six themes, each one standing for a System of Representation: TEXT, FIGURE, OBJECT, IMAGE, SPACE and LIGHT. Within every system, a variety of issues dealing with the concept of Representation are addressed in an interdisciplinary manner. It is a compulsory course lasting three semesters, in the second and third year of a five-year architectural program. It is being offered since the academic year 1999/2000.

1. The concept of Representation

Representation is the main subject matter of this course. Commonly, by Representation we understand something opposed to the reality of an object, as when we speak of the image or likeness of something. In a broader sense, Representation should be considered as a conceptual framework mediating between subject and object; it is this that makes reality intelligible. In this regard, this mediating structure might be considered as real as reality itself: the *reality of representation* is then opposed to the *representation of reality*.²

The notion of Representation is eminently philosophical and, as such, it transcends the boundaries in which knowledge has been divided. As a matter of fact, the specific meaning of the concept varies for each discipline. In the arts, a *representation* is a form that fulfills an aesthetic purpose. In geometry, a *representation system* refers to specific conventions used to depict three-dimensional bodies in two dimensions (projective systems, like eye and axonometric perspective). In architecture, *representing* encompasses the expression of ideas or images through drawings (e.g. sketches, diagrams) or models (e.g. physical and digital models), as well as by means of graphic languages and conventions to represent a building at different scales, using plans, sections and elevations, for example. In linguistics, a language is thought of as a symbol system that *represents* the real world. In psychology, a *representation* is mostly considered as a subjective mental image whereas cognitive sciences are concerned with *objective representations*, like the conceptual structures involved in problem-solving.

Instead of looking at the manifestations of the concept of Representation in each discipline, we might consider it as a subject matter in its own. This way, Representation is not subsumed under a particular field, but rather the other way around: the different disciplines are encompassed by a unique notion of Representation. This is how Nelson Goodman understands it in *Languages of Art*, 1976, where he claims Representation to be a symbol system which is applicable both to the arts and to the sciences. According

by their peers; in IMAGE, they reason on the meanings of images previously collected in a digital library created by the class; in OBJECT, they participate in processes of form generation, developing objects collaboratively throughout successive stages; in SPACE, they create spatial structures and narratives in collaboration; and in LIGHT they transform spaces by modifying the lighting conditions.

The three components of the learning environment are related in the following ways (Figure 2):

- *Theory -> Exercises*: Theoretical issues raised during lectures are subsequently explored in the exercises. Exercises are not meant to be practical applications of the theory but extensions of it. Students are not asked to solve a particular problem but to put together the issues they want to address.
- *Exercises -> Web system*: Exercises are carried out individually and collaboratively. Individual works collected in the web system are exposed to the critical scrutiny of the class. In the Web, students can comment or further develop their peers' works. Moreover, in accordance with the participative nature of the Net, they become engaged in collaborative processes of form and space creation.
- *Web system -> Theory*: The theoretical issues arise as a result of establishing relations between 'theory bits'. This open-ended theoretical framework fits the nature of the Net, where relationships acquire more importance than the issues themselves. Students are expected to participate in this process of knowledge construction, adding items to the network of ideas.

The course SDR combines web-based technologies with traditional education in the classroom (blended learning model). Rather than replacing face-to-face contact with the Web, new learning spaces are added to the traditional classroom-based model: spaces where the collective work of the class is visualized in a unique manner thanks to the support of technology, allowing students to further reflect upon the interrelationships between works, between ideas, between individuals.

Figure 1. Multi-inter-transdisciplinarity.

Figure 2. The three components of the learning environment.

5. Systems of Representation

After the introduction to the pedagogic basis of the course, the content, method and exercises for each one of the six themes are summarized in the following sections.

5.1 System of Representation: TEXT

The lectures in the theme TEXT encompass different areas of knowledge, including linguistics (syntax and semantics, generative grammar), cognition (semantic networks, concept maps), graphic design (typography, posters, advertisement, media), interactive media (interface design, interactivity), and art and architectural theory (aesthetic principles of modern art and architecture). The individual exercise consists on analyzing a manifesto from the European artistic avant-garde¹¹. Each student makes an interpretation of its content and explains it to the class using a multimedia authoring tool (Figure 3). Afterwards, the content of the manifesto is explained in three concepts which are introduced in the web environment SDR: NETWORKING[TEXT]. This way, a critical vocabulary summarizing all the texts analyzed by students is collectively created (Figure 4). The next step in the collaborative work is to establish relationships between pairs of concepts in the vocabulary. This is done in a straightforward and simple manner using an interface specifically designed for this task (Figure 5). These relationships, collaboratively constructed by the class, are then visualized as a concept map (Figure 6).

Figure 3. Interpretation of Loos' Ornament and Crime. Student: Agustí Canadell.

Figure 4. Critical vocabulary collaboratively constructed.

The subsequent exploration of the semantic spaces embodied in the map becomes a source of new knowledge, both for students and teachers¹². In this context, the conceptual map becomes an abstract machine, an artificial construct that allows learners to produce meaning in interaction with it. For constructivist pedagogy, concept maps appear to be an excellent technique to promote knowledge construction, both for individuals and groups (Novak & Gowin, 1984). In this exercise, the concept map is the expression of the knowledge which has been collectively constructed by the class¹³. The visualization of the relationships between concepts not only facilitates an understanding of each one of the five texts but, most important, makes it possible to establish connections between them (e.g. between the notion of form in Loos and in Mies). These relationships are first explained by students in the map and later in a short text which is

images and texts submitted by students contribute to the enhancement of the ideas presented in the class.

As in the theme TEXT, there are also activities which are carried out outside the boundaries of the classroom, in the School. In this case, it is the collaborative creation of a pavement using printed compositions which are placed on the floor following the associations previously established in the web system. (Figure 12).

Figure 11. Extension of a class discussion in the web space.

Figure 12. Pavement constructed collaboratively.

5.3 System of Representation: IMAGE

The lectures in this theme introduce students to image, in its philosophical, aesthetic, technical and cultural dimensions. The network of theory bits includes myth and religion (Narcissus, Genesis), philosophy (Plato and the distinction idea/image), history of photography (from the camera obscura to digital imaging), aesthetics (cross-breeding relationships between art forms, like painting and photography, film and digital media) and advertisement (posters, photomontage). This inclusive approach, which has the ultimate goal of creating a transdisciplinary discourse around image, conforms to the purposes of the emerging area of Visual Studies.¹⁷

Figure 13. Digital library of the mediascape. Photo: Henri Cartier-Bresson.

Figure 14. Digital library of the urbanscape. Student: Anaïs Palacio.

Individual and collaborative exercises are carried out during six weeks, following this sequence:

1. *Perception of image in the mediascape.* Students choose three images from any media (television, video, film, press, Internet) and explain their meaning in a short text. With this exercise they become aware of the visual environment created by the media. Images and texts are submitted to the web-based environment SDR: NETWORKING [IMAGE] to collaboratively create a digital library (Figure 13)

2. *Perception of image in the urbanscape.* Students observe the urban environment through the photographic camera. With this exercise they are confronted with the task of discovering visual meaning in their physical surrounding (e.g. the city of Barcelona). Photographs of the city are organized in categories (underground city, city in motion, inner city, private space, monuments,...) within the web-based environment (Figure 14).

3. *Associating images.* Once the digital library with images taken from the media and from the urban environment has been completed, the next task is to group images explaining what they have in common through a concise text. This task is performed on an interface where images can be dragged to the bottom of the window to make a group (Figure 15). With this exercise students develop the necessary skill for interpreting images and associating meanings to them.

4. *Photomontage.* The final goal of the sequence of exercises is the creation of a photomontage which conveys a personal idea of the contemporary city. The photomontage is composed of images previously collected in the digital library (Figure 16).

Figure 15. Interface to group images.

Figure 16. Photomontage library.

To foster links between the classroom and the web-based learning space, a short text summarizing a topic discussed in the class about the theme IMAGE, is posted by the teacher to trigger a forum discussion. In turn, the comments posted by students are discussed again in the classroom.

At the end of the exercise, photographs and photomontages are shown at an exhibition in the School. Also, a selection of the images are printed as postcards and distributed freely in dispensers located in the city. Besides, any Internet user can send these images as digital cards (see www.bcnimatges.net). This way, students' work

transcends the limits of the classroom: physically, through the postcards distributed in public places in the city and digitally, through Internet.

5.4 System of Representation: OBJECT

The theme OBJECT deals with the generation of three-dimensional abstract forms according to three formal languages: line, plane and solid. As in previous themes, modern art works are a fundamental reference: the objects of the Russian Constructivists and De Stijl, but also three-dimensional works from later artists like Jorge Oteiza, Anthony Caro, Sol Lewitt or Richard Serra are presented and discussed. Besides the digressions on modern art there are lectures on morphology, explaining the structure of minerals, the growth of plants, and the relation between the shape of an animal and its motion (fishes in water, birds in air).

In this theme, students first create an abstract object based on the language of the line and plane, and make a series of views (static and dynamic). The objects are modelled with commercial software (AutoCAD, 3dStudioMax) as well as with an application called I-LINE (intuitive line), created especially for the course. With this tool, three-dimensional forms can be created directly in 3d space, by simply dragging the mouse on the screen. The objects are described by three concepts which summarize their essential characteristics. The object (3d data) and its description (images, texts) is sent to the web system SDR: NETWORKING [OBJECT] (Figure 17). Then, the class work can be visualized by student name, object name or concept definition. The subsequent collaborative tasks consist of: 1. Picking another colleague's object in order to continue transforming it 2. Attaching concepts to other student's objects 3. Making groups with the objects, describing the characteristics they share.

Figure 17. Language of the plane: library of objects. Student: Marcos Cabello.

Figure 18. Language of the solid: collaborative process.

The section of the exercise dealing with the language of the solid is developed collaboratively from the start. The purpose of the exercise is to participate in a collaborative development process of a three-dimensional object carried out in successive stages (Figure 18). There is a vocabulary of transformation rules that has been collectively created by the class before the beginning of the process. The class is divided into groups of 10-12 students. Each group starts with a seed object (e.g. a cube) and has two days to transform it, applying some of the rules previously defined. Along with the formal transformation, the student sends a brief explanation of what has happened to the object. This way, the written description facilitates the creation of a

There are three kinds of exercises in this theme, according to this sequence: 1. representing the physical experience of space by means of a cognitive map 2. expressing an idea of space with an animation, using video and/or digital models. 3. creating a geometric space 'from within' using IN-Space, an application created especially for this course which allows the user to 'dig' spaces along each axis of the Cartesian space.

The purpose of the first exercise is to stir up student's sensibility of the student towards space, paying attention to the relation between body and space, orientation mechanisms, the activities occurring in space, and the meanings assigned to places. The task is to represent a personal experience of space with a cognitive map, using an ad hoc graphic language.

The goal of the animation is to effectively transmit an idea of space to the spectator, using the language of the cinema. The work can be done with material recorded by video cameras or, alternatively, building a three-dimensional model on the computer. In both cases, basic cinematographic techniques (storyboarding, narratives, and transitions) need to be applied. Montages are done with commercial software, like Premiere or Cinema4D.

The last exercise is done with the application IN_SPACE, created for this course. Spaces can be shaped 'from within', as the cursor is moved along the axes of a three-dimensional Cartesian space made up of cells. Starting from a cell located at the center, a space can be projected outwards and inwards along any of the three axes with a mouse click. Sounds, images and texts can be added to qualify any cell composing a space. Cells with attributes act as nexus linking one space to another. An interface allows students to get into the spaces created by their peers and to establish links between them, based on the cell's shared attributes. (Figure 21)

Figure 21. IN_SPACE.

Figure 22. Installation NETWORKING: SPACE (S).

The double-screen installation NETWORKING: SPACE (S) (see http://web.salleurl.edu/arc/netspace_s/) was thought of to continue students' work beyond the limits of the course (Figure 22). Animations displayed in one screen were selected by participants to be displayed in a second screen. As the animation was playing, words taken from the description students gave of their work could be dragged inside the space. Also, the animation could be stopped at any moment to write a new word inside a space. This way, the sensations the perception of a space was arising in

the visitor could be recorded and indexed. Spaces and words were the building blocks for constructing a universe of relationships in a collaborative manner. When the installation entered the stand-by mode, an automated procedure played back the spaces, generating spatial hypernarratives from the narratives built by students and visitors while jumping from one space to another following the thread of associations set by words.

5.6 System of Representation: LIGHT

The theme LIGHT deals with the relationship between light and space. Light is understood in two ways: 1. in the physical sense, as energy source which makes objects visible to senses 2. in the intellectual sense, as the knowledge that makes things intelligible. The topics addressed in the lectures include: the notion of light in Platonic and Scholastic philosophy; the representation of light in painting in the Dutch and Italian schools; the representation of light in impressionist paintings; the relationship between light, form and space in architecture; and the dematerialization of form and space through light in minimal art.

The goal of the exercise is to create an atmosphere using natural and artificial light as the main space-forming element. Typically, a geometric envelope must exist first so that its surfaces become visible through the action of light. However, this precedence of geometry over light -which architects take for granted- might be reversed, as the work of James Turrell suggests.¹⁹

Figure 23. Individual exercise: creating an atmosphere. Student: Jesús Martí.

Figure 24. Collaborative exercise: transforming a space modifying lighting conditions.

Exercises are carried out individually and collaboratively, with physical models and renderings. The purpose of the exercises is to develop the perceptual mechanisms to see and represent the effect of light on space: the illumination of surfaces and materials; the character of light and the atmosphere of a space; the changing character of a space over time; and the interplay between geometry, material, and light. The goal is to create an atmosphere with simple geometric envelopes and a limited choice of materials, stressing light over geometry and texture (Figure 24).

6. Conceptual implications of the integration of computer technology in architectural education

Throughout history, education reformists have felt compelled to bridge the gap between the social, economic and cultural conditions in each epoch and the prevailing education systems. Such was the goal of the reforms postulated by Rousseau, Fröbel, Pestalozzi and Montessori. And it was a goal of the Bauhaus too, as Gropius had proclaimed in 1924: “Its responsibility [the Bauhaus’] is to educate men and women to understand the world in which they live and to invent and create forms symbolizing that world. For this reason the educational field must be enlarged on all sides and extended into neighboring fields, so that the effects of new experiments may be studied”²⁰

Today, we are witnessing that information and communication technologies are quickly transforming the world, at the economic, social and cultural levels. As a result, there is an increasing gap between a discipline-based education and the demands for a more complex and global culture, which -as Morin has claimed- calls for “a way of thinking that can grasp text and context, individual and environment, local and global, the multidimensional –in a word, the complex”.²¹

If architects need to understand the world they live in to contribute to its construction –in its intellectual and material sense-, then our pedagogic systems need to integrate information technologies in the creative processes, at the individual and collaborative levels. First, at the individual level, architecture students should be able to master computer technologies to the extent that they can conceive and develop, express and communicate their ideas with them. This does not mean to train them to be efficient users of computer applications. Rather, they should learn to think with them, to communicate through them²². Secondly, at the collaborative level, we should exploit the potential of ICT to promote a constructivist philosophy of education in which both students and teachers actively participate in the creation of knowledge.

The course SDR aims at providing students with the mental equipment to understand the contemporary world. With the strategy we have adopted, the integration of information technologies becomes an opportunity to create an innovative and comprehensive pedagogic framework that responds to the conceptual and technological challenges of our time. This structure puts interdisciplinary knowledge, collaborative design and thinking processes, and information and communication technologies into relation. We believe that architectural students educated in this pedagogic frame develop the capacities that will later facilitate a rich exchange with other disciplines and a creative collaboration with other professionals, in an increasingly global world.

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programmed by Jordi Vidal, Multimedia Engineer. The applications I-GRID and I-LINE were developed by Álvaro Sicilia, Technical Engineer in Computer Science, using the Object ARX libraries from Autodesk. IN-SPACE has been programmed by Gonçal Costa, Multimedia Engineer, using Macromedia Director MX.

References

- Bill, M. (1949) The mathematical way of thinking in the visual art of our time. In Emmer, M. (ed.) (1995) *The Visual Mind. Art and Mathematics*. The MIT Press, Cambridge.
- Bonsiepe, G. (2003) The Relevance of the Ulm School of Design Today. In *Ulmer Modelle-Modelle nach Ulm/ Hochschule für Gestaltung Ulm, 1953-1968*. Hatje Cantz, Ostfildern-Ruit.
- Hamelin, O. (1952) *Essai sur les éléments principaux de la représentation*. Presses Universitaires de France, Paris.
- Goodman, N. (1976) *Languages of Art*. Hackett Publishing Co., Indianapolis.
- Bayer, H., Gropius, W., Gropius, I. (1984). *Bauhaus 1919-1928*. Secker & Warburg, London.
- Hamelin, O. (1925) *Essai sur les éléments principaux de la représentation*. Félix Alcan, Paris.
- Kepes, G. (1947) *Language of vision*. Paul Theobald, Chicago.
- Madrazo, L., Quílez, J. M., Sicilia, A. (2002) Design knowledge as interaction between form and shape: A pedagogic case study. *Digital Creativity* 13 (3) 129-143.
- McAleese, R. (2000). Skill Acquisition: The Curious Case of Information Searching. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 8 (1), 23-49.
- McLuhan, M. (1994) *Understanding Media. The Extensions of Man*. The MIT Press, Cambridge.
- Mirzoeff, N. (1999) *An introduction to visual culture*. Routledge, New York.
- Moles, A., Rohmer, É. (1972) *Psychologie de l'espace*, Tournai: Casterman.
- Morin, E. (2001) *Seven complex lessons in education for the future*. Unesco Publishing, Paris.
- Noever, P. (ed.) (1999) *James Turrell. The other horizon*. MAK & Cantz Verlag, Vienna and Ostfildern-Ruit.
- Rajchman, J. (2000) *The Deleuze Connections*. The MIT Press, Cambridge.
- Rodowick, D. N. (2001). *Reading the Figural. Or, Philosophy after the New Media*. Duke University Press, Durham & London.
- Scardamalia, M., Bereiter, C., Brett, C., Burtis, P.J., Calhoun, C., and Smith Lea, N. (1992) Educational Applications of a Networked Communal Database. *Interactive Learning Environments* 2 (1).
- Wick, R. (2000) *Teaching at the Bauhaus*. Hatje Cantz, Ostfildern-Ruit.

¹ See <http://www.salleurl.edu/sdr/description> for a comprehensive description of the content, methods, tools of this course, as well as for a selection of students' works.

² This neo-kantian view of the notion of representation has been described by Hamelin with the following words: "La représentation, contrairement à la signification étymologique du mot, car il faut bien emprunter les mots au sens commun, ne représente pas, ne reflète pas un objet et un sujet qui existeraient